

PORO-ELASTIC ACOUSTIC META MATERIALS WITH IMPROVED SOUND ABSORPTION

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ABSTRACT

In the last 20 years there has been very little progress in developing materials with improved sound absorption, particularly in the low frequency region. This paper summarizes work in developing and testing a new class of poro-elastic materials, based upon meta approaches, with improved sound reduction. In line with the meta approach, the new materials consist of a composite matrix structure supporting embedded periodic elements. The paper presents both experimental and numerical results demonstrating the improved sound absorption and transmission loss achieved with these materials.

1 ACOUSTIC META MATERIALS

Acoustic Meta Materials (AMM) are generally defined as materials with properties not readily available in nature. Terms such as “negative stiffness” etc add to the allure of meta materials with the implication that unusual behavior can be achieved. Meta materials achieve their performance characteristics through embedded resonant elements. There are two general classes of meta materials. The first consists of stationary embedded wave scatterers embedded in a matrix in order to achieve impedance variation due to the wave resonance and anti-resonance behavior between the elements[1]. This implies that the embedded elements must both transmit and reflect the impinging wave front thus a perforated plate structure is a common scattering element[1]. The scattering elements are usually arranged in a periodic fashion in order to achieve stop band wave behavior where the propagating wave number component becomes imaginary leading to decaying waves. The second type of meta material consists of individual resonators embedded in the matrix[2]. The effect of these resonators is to modify the impedance of the matrix material via dynamic coupling. Both of these types of meta materials will be considered in this paper.

2 PORO-ELASTIC ACOUSTIC META MATERIALS

In this paper we will describe results from investigating two type of poro-elastic acoustic meta materials[3,4,5]. For these systems, the matrix material is chosen to be a standard poro-elastic sound absorbing foam such as Melamine or Polyimide. In the resonant type AMM, small mass spheres are embedded in the foam matrix in either an aperiodic or periodic arrangement. The small masses combine with the natural stiffness and damping of the foam to create an array of mass-spring damper systems with resonant frequencies. At frequencies near to the resonance of the embedded masses, the sound absorption and transmission loss of the standard foam will be shown to be significantly altered. When the AMM is attached to an elastic structure such as a panel, the dynamics of the AMM significantly alters the sound transmission characteristic of the panel. In the non resonant form of the poro-elastic AMM, very thin polymer microporous sheets are embedded in the foam at periodic locations.

2.1 Heterogeneous poro-elastic acoustic materials

An early form of poro-elastic AMM was investigated at Virginia Tech in the early 2000's by Prof. Fuller and his team. It consisted of a poro-elastic foam matrix into which were embedded an array of small masses at various depths and spatial locations. A schematic of the arrangement is shown in

Figure 1. The small masses combined with the natural stiffness and mechanical damping of the foam to create an array of mass-spring-damper (MSD) vibrators embedded in the foam. This system was called at Heterogeneous (HG) material[3,5] but in reality can be seen to be an early form of a practical Acoustic Meta Material. The stiffness of the foam and thus the resonant frequencies of the MSD's depends upon the depth at which the mass is embedded. Thus when the foam is attached to a distributed elastic structure, it is very similar situation to an array of MSD's with a range of resonant frequencies being attached to the structure at different spatial locations. If an HG material is attached to vibrating distributed elastic structure such as a thin metal panel, then it would be expected to provide global reduction of vibration and coupled sound radiation over the resonant frequency range of the MSD's.

Figure 1. Schematic arrangement of an HG acoustic material.

Figure 2 presents experimental test results where a thin 1mm, 4ft by 4ft aluminum panel was mounted in a test hole of a transmission loss test facility. The source side was reverberant and the receiving side was anechoic. The spatially averaged radiated sound normal intensity was measured at the panel surface using a scanning intensity probe and is thus proportional to the acoustic power transmitted through the panel.

Figure 2. Spatially averaged sound intensity versus frequency.

The HG material was constructed from a 4ft by 4ft section of Melamine foam of two and three inch thicknesses containing 50 spherical masses of 6gm weight each. The masses were embedded in a random pattern of depth and span locations. Previous testing of a single mass embedded in two inch Melamine has shown the depth range provides a MSD resonant frequency range of 50 to 200Hz. Examining Figure 2, the bare panel can be seen to transmit sound power at peaks corresponding to resonant modes of the panel. Attaching the standard foam to the panel surface by light gluing can be seen to, in general, provide negligible attenuation of transmitted sound power except near 80Hz. When the masses are added to the foam to create the HG system, the transmitted sound power can be seen to be significantly attenuated from 70 to 180Hz, a bandwidth which corresponds to the resonant frequency range of the embedded MSD's. In terms of weight, the two inch HG system weighs less than the three inch standard Melamine foam system and yet significantly outperforms it in terms of sound attenuation. These tests illustrate the promise of resonant dynamics, which is the core physical aspect of meta material, in providing enhanced low frequency performance with little weight addition.

2.2 Poro-elastic AMM with embedded masses

With the rise in interest in Acoustic Meta Materials around 2010, it was decided to modify the HG material by arranging the embedded spherical masses in a periodic fashion to take advantage of the resonant wave scattering of the static periodic masses in addition to their dynamic behaviour observed in the HG material discussed above[3,5]. The new AMM was analysed using Finite Element Analysis(FEA) and experimental testing in a standing wave tube. This necessarily limited the incident acoustic wave to a plane wave of normal incidence. Figure 3(a) shows a schematic of the AMM and Figure 3(b) shows a section of a constructed sample where the embedded masses are spherical steel masses embedded in Melamine foam. Different configurations of AMM were studied, including polypropylene and hollow aluminium masses as well as polyimide, polyurethane and fiberglass poro-elastic matrix materials of different thicknesses.

Figure 3. Poro-elastic AMM (a) schematic arrangement, (b) section of a constructed sample.

Figure 4 presents example results from the FEA of the 1-D system as well as from experimental measurement of a free standing sample of AMM located in standing wave/transmission loss test tube. In this case the AMM sample was located in the centre of the test tube and the absorption coefficient and transmission loss of the sample measured using two upstream microphones and two downstream microphones and cross spectral techniques to deconvolve the positive and negative traveling acoustic waves in the standard testing approach. From Figure 4 it can be seen that there is good agreement between the FEA and testing results thus validating the FEA model. The FEA can thus be used to efficiently investigate the physics and dynamics of the AMM over a range of parameters. Addition of

the masses to the standard poro-elastic material to create the AMM, can be seen to significantly increase the sound absorption and transmission loss of the standard foam at low frequencies. The absorption coefficient can be seen to nearly double in value at 250Hz which is a very significant result. Likewise the transmission loss of the AMM can be seen to be increase by 5 to 10dB near 250 Hz which is also significant.

Figure 4. FEA and test results for poro-elastic AMM (a) absorption coefficient, (b) transmission loss.

Various productized versions of the AMM have been manufactured and tested in practical applications to machinery housings, aircraft fuselage panels, launch vehicle payload fairing and automobile instrument panels. Figure 5(a) shows a productized version of the AMM called Lo Wave applied to a machinery housing around an electrical motor[6]. Figure 5(b) presents the measured results for the noise radiated by the machine with no treatment, standard fiberglass poro-elastic treatment and HG/AMM treatment of the same thickness, constructed from a fiberglass matrix and embedded small masses. The HG/AMM can be seen to provide superior noise reduction over the conventional blanket between 30 and 130Hz.

Figure 5. Product version of the poro-elastic AMM, (a) installation, (b) test result[6].

2.3 Poro-elastic AMM with embedded microporous sheets.

In an attempt to develop lighter poro-elastic AMM, the embedded masses described above were replaced with embedded thin, polymer, microporous(MPP) sheets[4,5]. The MPP sheets were embedded in the matrix of poro-elastic material at equal spacing thus creating a periodic scattering system. MPP sheets consist of a thin sheet of material such as plastic or metal containing micro holes with a small percent open area(POA). It has previously been demonstrated that MPP sheets can be used to increase sound absorption at low frequencies due to the damping provided by the vibrating air squeezing through the micro holes[7]. Our arrangement of using multiple MPP sheets as a component of an AMM is novel but we do take advantage of the known physics of their behaviour, namely wave transmission with damping and reflection. In addition it should be noted that previous acoustic AMM such as cloaks etc. were constructed from periodic layers of stacked perforated plates[1] which is a related system(the holes are much larger and transmission directly through the plates is negligible). Figure 6 shows an arrangement of an AMM constructed from Melamine foam with four embedded MPP sheets. This system is designed for application to a launch vehicle payload fairing and the foam is of 4inch thickness, the MPP sheets are 0.27mm thick, the holes are of 0.2mm diameter and the POA is 0.8%.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. AMM with embedded MPP sheets, (a) assembled (b) MPP sheets displaced to show their structure.

Figures 7 and 8 presents the measured absorption coefficient and transmission loss of the AMM with different number of MPP sheets respectively. The tests were performed in a standing wave and transmission loss(TL) tube respectively and thus represent normal incidence, plane acoustic wave results The addition of the MPP sheets can be seen to significantly increase the sound absorption at low frequencies between 100 to 350Hz.

Figure 7. Measured normal incidence absorption coefficient of the AMM.

The transmission loss results in Figure 8 show that the addition of the MPP sheets increases the TL at both low and high frequencies with an increase of close to 20dB observed at 1.5kHz with three MPP sheets. This is a very significant result of increasing TL of the poro-elastic Melamine foam with negligible mass increase.

Figure 8. Measured normal incidence transmission loss of the AMM.

In a more practical test, the random incidence absorption coefficient of a 4ft by 4ft section of 2inch thick AMM consisting of Melamine foam with three embedded MPP sheets was measured in a large reverberation chamber by NASA staff-see Figure 9. The results are shown in Figure 9 along with transfer function matrix modelling of the AMM material utilizing the calculated transfer function of the sections of Melamine foam and the MPP sheets(utilizing Maa’s equations[7]). The AMM is shown to provide double the absorption coefficient compared to the standard Melamine foam of the

same thickness. It is interesting that the absorption curve for the AMM appears as the curve for the standard Melamine foam shifted to lower frequencies. This can be physically explained as follows. The periodic scatterers of AMM's are known to slow the phase speed of the acoustic wave transmission through their structure[2]. Thus if the wave speed reduces so does the wavelength at a constant frequency and the sound absorption is increased due to the shorter wavelength. Alternatively, the AMM appears as it is operating at a higher frequency due to the lower wave speed. This is one of the advantages of AMM; their ability to lower wave speed. The other is their ability to vary impedance spatially and thus cause wave refraction as utilized in acoustic cloaks.

Figure 9. Measurement of random incidence absorption coefficient of poro-elastic AMM in a large reverberation chamber at NASA LaRC.

Figure 9. Measured and predicted absorption coefficient of AMM under random incidence sound fields.

Productized versions of the AMM based upon MPP sheets have been constructed and tested in a number of practical applications such as noise reduction in aircraft and automobiles. Recently a flight test of an AMM acoustic liner installed in the trim of a passenger jet aircraft was carried out. The AMM material was commercially manufactured to exactly replace the standard acoustic liner

components with the same thickness and shape. It was constructed from the standard green fiberglass poro-elastic material with three embedded thin, polymer MPP sheets and bagged in the standard Kapton material. The cabin interior sound levels were measured with an array of 12 microphones located at head height in the forward and aft cabin in two separate flight tests, one with standard acoustic material and the other with AMM. The operational flight conditions were kept the same for both tests. Significantly, the AMM when compared to the standard material, was found to provide an additional 10dB noise reduction at low frequencies near 10 to 50Hz with a negligible weight increase.

2.4 Active AMM

Since AMMs are dependent upon resonant conditions to achieve their superior performance, they are narrowband materials and this limits their application. Work has been carried out to investigate the potential of adding active inserts in order to widen the AMM frequency band of operation. Previous work considered active AMM for controlling beam vibration[8]. Small inertial actuators have been used to replace some of the embedded masses of the poro-elastic AMM as shown in Figure 10. The inertial actuators are of similar weight and size to the static embedded masses and thus provide similar passive resonant dynamics in motion and wave scattering. When driven by oscillating electrical signals, these inertial actuators provide vibration inputs to the foam matrix and thus can modify its dynamics in a controllable manner. The active AMM was tested in standing wave tube utilizing a digital feedforward Filtered X control approach[9] shown schematically in Figure 11. In this approach the upstream microphone sensor picks up the impinging noise field from the standing wave tube noise speaker. The digital control algorithm adapts to minimize the sound and the downstream error microphone by applying time varying control signals to the embedded inertial actuators which in term modify the dynamics of the foam matrix.

Figure 10. Cross section of a polyimide based AMM with 10 polypropylene masses and two active masses and (b) close up of an active mass.

Figure 11. Schematic arrangement of active AMM positioned in a standing wave tube and digital active control system.

Results from the testing of the active AMM, utilizing both tonal and a broad band white noise signal are given in Figure 12. The active inputs can be seen to increase the sound attenuation of the acoustic wave transmitted through the AMM by close to 20dB for tonal noise and 10dB from 50 to 110Hz for broadband noise. The physical mechanisms of how this is achieved is presently under investigation, however it is thought that the active vibration inputs modify the impedance distribution throughout the foam matrix. The result is a modification of the wave transmission through the foam for an enhanced AMM effect.

Figure 12. Performance of the active AMM (a) 130Hz noise signal (b) 250Hz noise signal and (c) white noise signal.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Two different arrangement of poro-elastic Acoustic Meta Material have been discussed in this paper. The first kind consist of embedded spherical masses in the foam matrix while in the second kind, microporous sheets are embedded. Both systems have been demonstrated numerically and experimentally to have a high absorption coefficient and transmission loss compared to the standard foam at low frequencies. Due to its construction, the poro-elastic material is easily scalable to practical size in cost effective manufacturing. The poro-elastic AMM thus has high potential for an improved low frequency, lightweight, compact noise control treatment which is designable. The use of active inputs in the form of small inertial actuators has also been shown to have potential to widen the frequency range of the poro-elastic AMM attenuation.

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